

SUPREME HRM: A Proposed Enhanced Framework in PRIME HRM

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Abstract

This paper is an empirical study that highlights the performance productivity of the government workforce using PRIME Human Resource Management (HRM) in the Philippines. The findings postulate PRIME HRM which creates a significant impact on organizational and individual performance. Nonetheless, beyond the successful employee engagement associated with PRIME HRM, the study posits the relative experiences of the workforce which adversely affects their well-being and wellness. To delve into these employee experiences the study integrated Sustainable HRM and checked on the status of the workforce without compromising the organizational performance. Eventually, the two tenets were merged to propose a holistic approach in HRM by way of methodological triangulation. This integration is called SUPREME HRM framework which is an intervention in managing the paradoxes between strategic employee engagement and sustainable employee experience that supports the improvement of wellness, and well-being, equitable to the organizational performance.

Key Words: *SUPREME HRM, PRIME HRM, Sustainable HRM*

1. INTRODUCTION

In the past decade, there has been a significant transformation in the field of Human Resources (HR) within organizations. This transformation has involved the incorporation of various concepts, functions, and scopes, moving away from traditional personnel management towards more advanced approaches such as Human Resource Management (HRM), Strategic Human Resource Management (SHRM), and in contemporary, Sustainable Human Resource Management (SuHRM) (Indiparambil, 2019). While the recognition of HR's role in cultivating a competitive advantage is widely accepted, there has been a tendency to neglect the welfare and well-being of employees in the pursuit of organizational goals and targets.

The Civil Service Commission (CSC), the Philippine government's central human resources authority, has developed several HR initiatives to improve public sector HRM and organizational development practices. To fulfill these responsibilities, CSC established the PRIME HRM (Program to Institutionalize Meritocracy and Excellence in Human Resource Management) in 2012. It recognizes outstanding HR practices across all levels of employees and equipping government institutions with the resources they need to improve their HRM operations (Civil Service Commission Memorandum Circular No. 3, 2012). PRIME HRM as CSC's SHRM version focuses on the connection between strategy and HRM, nonetheless, SHRM gives more attention to the latter (Kramar, 2022). Its plans and procedures are enhanced by the inclusion of SuHRM.

In the Philippines, there are more than 3,400 government agencies enrolled for PRIME HRM accreditation and recognition in 2023. Only 18% have achieved the PRIME HRM

maturity level II for the last 10 years of implementation. In Region IV, as of August 2023, the data shows that only 13.47% of the enrolled government agencies have achieved the bronze level. Gaps such as the emergence of improvement opportunities aligned with global trends for the future of HR, and the anticipated future needs as a result of current demands arose during the program's decade of implementation (CSC OM no. 1, s. 2022). Other gaps are humanistic sustainable HRM practices such as the provisions for wellness and well-being programs, commitment, motivation, and satisfaction of employees (Castro & Edralin, 2018). Likewise, a challenge is also with HR officers in their competencies towards the experience and engagement of the workforce.

The study determined the impact of PRIME HRM practices through the lens of SuHRM. This led to the merger of the two tenets (PRIME HRM and SuHRM) into SUPREME HRM. SUPREME-HRM is an acronym that stands for Sustainable Program for Reinforcement in Establishing Meritocracy and Excellence in Human Resource Management. The enhanced framework is a reinforcement of PRIME HRM through the lens of sustainability. This new approach balances the process-oriented HR practices of PRIME HRM and the people-oriented HR practices of SuHRM (Aslanertik & Çolak, 2021). Combining the two makes SUPREME HRM practices achieve premium functions in HRM and can be colloquially considered PRIME HRM 2.0.

2. METHODOLOGY

The study used a mixed-method explanatory sequential design, which involves successive periods of gathering quantitative and then qualitative data. The design may "triangulate" findings by comparing quantitative and qualitative data side by side for verification and confirmation (Creswell & Clark, 2011). Most of these data were collected from government institutions under the jurisdiction of the Civil Service Commission (CSC). The study participants are government career employees who had a minimum of one year of work experience in public service with agencies that are part of State Universities and Colleges (SUCs), Local Government Units (LGUs), Government-Owned and Controlled Corporations (GOCCs), and National Government Agencies (NGAs) that have achieved the PRIME HRM maturity level II bronze awardee.

The online survey questionnaire underwent pilot testing to determine the validity and reliability of the instrument. The quantitative phase uses a stratified probability sampling technique to ensure that participants were selected based on their knowledge of the topic and their ability to interpret the questionnaire (Parsons, 2017), as the variables of the study require in-depth familiarity with PRIME HRM. The questionnaire first assesses the demographic characteristics of the participants, then the status of PRIME HRM and SuHRM. The online survey questionnaire includes open-ended questions that were answered by the participants to determine the impact of PRIME HRM and SuHRM practices that closely describe their personal experiences in their agencies. Their answers were processed through a COWS (Challenges, Opportunities, Weaknesses, and Strengths) matrix analysis which deepened and enhanced the understanding of the quantitative results. In the end, the results of the quantitative and qualitative part were methodologically triangulated to form a proposed framework in line with contemporary trends in HRM.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Quantitative Results

The results of Cronbach Alpha for the pilot test of PRIME HRM practices demonstrated excellent reliability of the questionnaire, as indicated by a value of .986. Moreover, SuHRM practices exhibited excellent internal consistency and reliability of the questionnaire, as evidenced by a Cronbach's Alpha value of .951. Thus, the result of the survey tool is reliable and valid for the study.

The demographic profile of participants includes a diverse group of participants, with 66% representing National Government Agencies (NGAs), 24% from Local Government Units (LGUs), 3% from Government-Owned and Controlled Corporations (GOCCs), and 6% from State Universities and Colleges (SUCs). A significant majority (73%) of the participants involved in this study were categorized as Rank-and-File personnel. This finding entails the significance of understanding the perspectives and experiences of the majority workforce inside these organizations, particularly in the context of employment levels. The percentages of participants representing the Management and HRMO positions, specifically 18% and 9% respectively, highlight the significance of conducting a comprehensive examination of the viewpoints and experiences of individuals occupying senior management and HR roles within the context of PRIME HRM and SuHRM practices. Obtaining a deeper understanding of the viewpoints and challenges faced by personnel at different hierarchical levels contributes to a holistic comprehension of an organization's internal dynamics. This is one way of making them understand their employment while training the workforce more than compensating them, to develop strategies to retain them (Westover, 2014). The distribution of demographics, as indicated by the length of service, exhibits a diverse range of tenures. This observation highlights the need to seek input from personnel who have been with an organization for a long time to obtain a thorough grasp of the historical knowledge management and evolution of HRM practices inside those organizations (Afacan Fındıklı, 2015).

The status of PRIME HRM practices in Region IV holds a highly favorable perception. The consistent median score of 4.0 across all sectors suggests a widespread acknowledgment of the effectiveness and success of PRIME HRM practices which include recruitment, selection and placement, learning and development, performance management, and rewards and recognition. The existence of uniform positive opinions across many sectors indicates a notable degree of consistency in the effectiveness and implementation of PRIME HRM practices.

The status of SuHRM practices is generally positive in Region IV, with a consistent median score of 4.0 reflecting a favorable attitude across diverse governmental sectors. This positive score is in categories such as the opportunity for employee happiness in their working condition, sustainable employment policies, environmental consciousness, flexibility practices, and digitization and digital transformation. Although, CSC does not have an institutionalized program like in PRIME HRM about SuHRM practices, a thorough participant observation analysis indicates that agencies have given SuHRM practices a high priority, indicating a shared endeavor to promote a culture that prioritizes sustainability, environmental consciousness, and employee well-being.

3.2 Qualitative Results

The study draws analysis on how PRIME HRM implementation impacts the workforce using C.O.W.S. matrix analysis. In challenges, there are opportunities for reparation. This notion is supported by Meijen et al, (2020) that “in a challenge state, the perceived resources are sufficient to deal with the demands of the situation, whereas, in a threat state, the demands outweigh the perceived resources.”

The Figure 1 illustration provides a determination of the ‘Positive’ and ‘Negative’ responses of the participants towards the integration of its outcome. The positive is represented by the opportunities and strengths while the negative is seen in the challenges and weaknesses.

Employee	P O S I T I V E		
	C.O.W.S. Matrix Analysis	Opportunities	Strengths
N	Challenges	C1+O1	C1+S1
		C2+O2	C2+S2
E	1. Less Understanding of Systems	Bridging the gap in system understanding and workforce wellbeing.	Allowing the systems to highlight the welfare program
G	2. Unable to Embrace the Process	Bridging the gap for process inculcation to the workforce's life	Allowing the people to become fully aware of the process
A	Weaknesses	W1+O1	W1+S1
		W2+O2	W2+S2
T	1. Unmet Goals and Targets	Make realistic Goals and Targets to achieve the well-being of the workforce	Adjust goals and targets and ensure welfare programs for the workforce
I	2. Poor Work Performance	Optimize performance through life integration	Improve work performance by having a task that works for people
V			
E			

Figure1: C.O.W.S. Matrix Analysis

By considering challenges as chances to assess the welfare of employees, it can transform into circumstances that bolster the resilience of the organization. The process of converting vulnerabilities into advantageous possibilities enhances the effectiveness of the workforce, leading to a condition of symmetry by altering negative elements into positive ones. When the operational framework prioritizes the well-being of the workforce, it enhances its overall welfare while simultaneously upholding performance aims and targets. Weaknesses can be strategically leveraged as a chance to highlight the program's positive characteristics.

Furthermore, the Human Resource Management (HRM) Octad Balance is a by-product of the result of the COWS matrix analysis as presented in Figure 2. Even if there are predicaments in the implementation of PRIME HRM, the picture shows opportunities and strengths in its implementation as it opens a bigger impact aside from the SHRM implementation.

Figure 2: Human Resource Management (HRM) Octad Balance

The illustration gives priority to respecting individuals over the expectation of individuals serving the system. This implies that systems and processes must provide utmost importance to the welfare of employees, refraining from any form of sacrifice of their personal lives in the interest of the system's success. Utilizing existing strengths and opportunities to enhance systems is more advantageous than exposing resilient systems to weaknesses and opportunities that ultimately amplify deficiencies. Enhancing the capabilities of these systems can effectively address the challenges and mitigate their weaknesses, thereby improving overall performance. Emphasizing the value of an organization's workforce, which represents its core asset, has the potential to address challenges and rectify weaknesses that may lead to improve below-average performance. The impact of PRIME HRM and SuHRM is significant as it calls for the program to reinforce and balance its implementation not to neglect the welfare of the workforce and the organization, the wellness of the people and the agency as well as the well-being of the employee and the institution.

3.3 Methodological Triangulation

Quantitative results examine the influence of different demographic factors which demonstrates a comprehensive representation encompassing various types of organizations, employment categories, genders, years of service, and educational levels. The inclusion of individuals from diverse backgrounds with equal opportunity to share their thoughts and have experienced certain HRM approaches which enhances the comprehensiveness of the dataset, hence strengthening its overall quality (Ebie & Djebarni, 2011). The study reveals that individuals hold a positive opinion towards PRIME HRM practices, supported by the median score of 4.0, which highly indicates a generally positive attitude. Thus, PRIME HRM practices are widely accepted and effectively implemented throughout various government organizations. It implies that agencies are already capable of achieving level III in terms of practices. Also, an examination of SuHRM practices demonstrates a promising view among participants with median ratings of 4.0 across various organizational types. This finding suggests that the respondents see highly effective implementation of SuHRM practices.

The quantitative analysis illuminates the perspectives of participants regarding PRIME HRM to SuHRM practices. The statement showcases an overall optimistic perspective of both categories of HRM and emphasizes the possibility of their integration. The results of the study establish a basis for future investigation and adoption of HRM techniques that seek to improve organizational excellence and sustainability in HRM. The qualitative results provide comprehensive approach within the realm of HRM that prioritizes the improvement of agencies and the progression of employees. The impact of PRIME HRM has several challenges, which need a strong commitment to SuHRM practices. The results necessitate a strong digital infrastructure to enhance the efficiency of recruiting procedures and guarantee equity and openness in the selection and placement of individuals, as proposed by Dineen et al. (2004). The data entails the effective implementation of PRIME HRM can be enhanced by including SuHRM practices, which subsequently promote employee experience, wellness, and general well-being. Moreover, the integrated analysis has a thorough comprehension of the obstacles and possibilities linked to the execution of PRIME HRM and SuHRM practices utilizing a combination of quantitative and qualitative research outcomes. The fusion of the two approaches highlights the significance of proficient communication, efficient allocation of resources, and SuHRM practices in the successful implementation of PRIME HRM techniques (Mohiuddin et. al., 2022). The implementation of SuHRM strategies is of paramount importance in fostering an inclusive work environment, especially in bringing up employee resilience and outcomes for good values (Lu et. al., 2022). The importance of implementing a systematic approach in HRM strategies is highlighted by the integrated study, with specific attention given to Human Development (HD), Social Development (SD), Economic Acumen (EA), and Environmental Consciousness (EC). Thus, organizations strive to optimize the capabilities of their workforce and foster a favorable setting that promotes productivity, well-being, and sustainable development goals (Fallah Shayan et. al., 2022).

Consequently, the effective handling of paradoxical tensions constitutes a fundamental element within the context under consideration. This requires the establishment of a balanced and mutually beneficial state in which the full potential of the workforce is both explored and utilized, while also ensuring that employees are not subjected to exploitation or an undue burden of duties (Gaim et. al., 2022).

3.4 Proposed SUPREME HRM Framework

The SUPREME HRM enhanced framework functions as a supplementary approach to PRIME HRM, incorporating the pillars and domains of SuHRM. The new paradigm recognizes the connection between SuHRM and PRIME HRM to establish this framework. The objective is to assist employees in attaining their targets while simultaneously experiencing job satisfaction. It also tries to optimize employee performance, engagement, and overall work experiences by using a holistic HRM approach. Through this framework, government agencies may cultivate motivation and flexibility in workforces to build capabilities for attaining long-term goals.

Figure3. Proposed SUPREME HRM Framework

The adoption of the SUPREME HRM framework as shown in Figure 3, allows firms to enhance their HRM procedures that nurture a change-oriented workforce with impactful relationships between high-commitment work systems and improved employee behaviors (Li et. al., 2019). Moreover, the SUPREME HRM framework serves as a transformative tool for government agencies aiming to shift toward a more sustainable and people-oriented HRM (Palm et. al., 2020). This phenomenon results in the attainment of long-term success and cultivates a flourishing organizational culture. Its fundamental basis is comprised of HD, SD, EA, and EC.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the study proves that in high-performing firms, workers may encounter negative experiences. The majority of the workforce, comprised of individuals in the Rank and File, has limited involvement in setting up the PRIME HRM in their agencies. This hinders the level of acquaintance of the workforce which impedes a thorough understanding of the program's capabilities. The main advantage of PRIME HRM is its positive impact on the organization as a whole, particularly in terms of strategic operations and workforce engagement. This advantage is real even if individual employees do not experience significant personal improvements, as long as the agency can meet compliance requirements and gain recognition. The workforce recognizes that the practices of PRIME HRM are evident within the agency, which is advantageous as it enables them to achieve a high degree of proficiency in PRIME HRM practices. They are to improve the systems and processes, which can be somewhat arduous. At least at the moment, the data already shows that they are now capable of starting their journey to advance their maturity level. Though, the absence of an institutionalized program on SuHRM in the organization, several agencies have already promoted the practices and elements that will look after the welfare, wellness, and well-being of the organization and the workforce. The presence of SuHRM in the government agency

makes it easier to introduce the program for adaptation. When personnel are provided with a remarkable organizational experience, they are likely to retain their connection with the firm throughout their entire career until retirement. Furthermore, the study firmly concludes on merging PRIME HRM and SuHRM which is not only feasible but also highly recommended, as it would result in a holistic approach that addresses both organizational needs and the wellness of workers. SUPREME HRM as a result of the merger fosters an organizational environment that promotes both productivity and well-being, consequently serving as a crucial factor in the overall success and adaptability of the organization. It incorporates both process-oriented and people-oriented approaches to effectively achieve the objectives of the organization while simultaneously ensuring the sustainability of its workforce. Fostering individual well-being empowers them to assume a fundamental role within their family unit, effectively managing their professional responsibilities through a work and life balance. When the workforce encounters sustainable experience, strategic engagement will be achieved.

The study's practical implications provide compelling evidence supporting the feasibility of integrating SHRM with SuHRM. SHRM and SuHRM are not only viable but also progressively imperative for organizational settings. The integration presents an encompassing strategy that successfully aligns HR practices with the overarching strategic objectives and sustainable development goals of an organization. Incorporating these two tenets, organizations may develop a comprehensive and forward-thinking approach that promotes the long-term success of the organization as well as the positive well-being of its personnel, society as a whole, and the natural surroundings. Thus, the newly formulated framework presents an innovative viewpoint to improve performance and optimize the HR experience. The comprehensive approach has the strategic and sustainable value of HRM and will not only function as a program but also play a vital role in sustaining the organization and its personnel. Therefore, it is desirable to establish a policy that incorporates SUPREME HRM as an integral component of the organization's HRM strategy.

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